

Recurrent Neural Network Based Quantile Predictions of Airport Capacity

Benjamin Tolley, Jeremiah Budiman, James C. Jones
MIT Lincoln Laboratory
Lexington MA, USA

Abstract— In the domain of air traffic management, reliance on heuristic guidelines for determining airport capacity often leads to suboptimal Traffic Management Initiatives (TMIs). To address this issue, we propose a data-centric methodology that leverages recurrent neural networks (RNNs) to predict quantile distributions of future airport capacity. These networks analyze diverse inputs including weather forecasts, scheduled demand, time of day, and current airport capacity data to make accurate distributions of future airport acceptance rates. We trained our model on 2018 historical data and then performed testing and online training with 2019 data from 29 core US airports. The neural networks capture time dependence within the weather forecasts to generate deterministic predictions of airport capacity as well as forecasts of likely capacity scenarios. We examine the models’ performance across our 2019 case days to provide insights into the practical applications of our data-driven approach. By integrating advanced weather models, historical data, and comprehensive error assessment, we aim to offer a more accurate, reliable, and usable alternative to the current heuristic guidelines, thereby contributing to the growing body of research on data-centric approaches in air traffic management. This holistic approach holds promise for optimizing airport capacity management, and improving overall air traffic flow efficiency with variable risk profiles.

Keywords- *Airport Capacity; Ensemble Weather Forecasts; Recurrent Neural Network; Random Correlated Draws; Machine Learning*

I. INTRODUCTION

Weather conditions continue to pose a major challenge for air traffic management (ATM), contributing to approximately 50% of all delays within the U.S. national airspace system in 2023 [1]. Adverse weather conditions reduce airport and airspace capacity, impeding efficient resource utilization. Additionally, the inherent uncertainty in the timing and location of adverse weather events creates further disruptions at both strategic and tactical levels. To mitigate these challenges, air traffic managers implement traffic management initiatives (TMIs) such as ground delay programs (GDPs), ground stops, airspace flow programs (AFPs), and collaborative trajectory options programs

(CTOPs) to manage traffic flow. Tactical interventions like miles-in-trail (MIT) restrictions, time-based metering, and airborne holding are also employed to address short-term capacity and demand imbalances.

TMI planning strategies have grown increasingly sophisticated, incorporating techniques such as speed control to align demand with capacity in GDPs [2-4]. These measures have demonstrated numerous benefits, including increased efficiency, reduced fuel consumption, and improved operational predictability. Furthermore, advancements in metering systems and flight deck avionics are enhancing trajectory-based operations [5-8].

Accurate airport capacity predictions are crucial to the effectiveness of these strategies. They enable stakeholders to make informed decisions about resource allocation and delay management. However, traditional methods for estimating airport capacity often rely on simplified heuristics and rules-of-thumb, leading to inaccuracies that can exacerbate delays and inefficiencies. Discrepancies between current predicted and actual capacities underscore the need for more robust estimation methodologies with a focus on accurately representing the inherent uncertainty in capacity predictions based off weather forecasts.

To address this gap, researchers have explored various approaches, including scenario-based planning in GDPs, decision support systems enhanced with weather forecasts [9-10], statistical models integrating wind and traffic data [11], and time-lagged prediction models incorporating Terminal Aerodrome Forecasts (TAF) [12]. Machine learning techniques, combined with weather forecasts, have shown promise in improving capacity prediction. Single airport studies have shown promising results in predicting airport capacities and runway configurations at certain airports [13-15] while other studies have explored generalizing machine learning models to multiple airports in the National Airspace System (NAS) [16-17]. Despite these advancements, current models typically summarize uncertainty using single-point estimates or symmetric intervals, which obscure the directional risk and distributional characteristics of the forecast error. We propose a quantile-based approach enabling users to assess not just how uncertain a prediction is, but how that uncertainty is distributed across potential outcomes.

Our research focuses on predicting airport capacity for 29 core U.S. airports. Building on past research [12], we aim to forecast airport capacity as a quantile distribution rather than

DISTRIBUTION STATEMENT A. Approved for public release. Distribution is unlimited.

This material is based upon work supported by the Department of the Air Force under Air Force Contract No. FA8702-15-D-0001. Any opinions, findings, conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the Department of the Air Force.

© 2025 Massachusetts Institute of Technology.

Delivered to the U.S. Government with Unlimited Rights, as defined in DFARS Part 252.227-7013 or 7014 (Feb 2014). Notwithstanding any copyright notice, U.S. Government rights in this work are defined by DFARS 252.227-7013 or DFARS 252.227-7014 as detailed above. Use of this work other than as specifically authorized by the U.S. Government may violate any copyrights that exist in this work.

discrete values, enabling a more nuanced understanding of both best- and worst-case scenarios. By analyzing the quantile distribution of airport capacity predictions, operational decision-makers can identify potential risks and opportunities, allocate resources effectively, and develop contingency plans for different scenarios. By quantifying the variability and uncertainty in capacity predictions, our methodology provides air traffic managers and other stakeholders with the tools needed to assess risks and plan more effectively under uncertain conditions.

Through a combination of advanced weather forecasts, demand modeling, and machine learning, we propose a predictive framework that offers enhanced accuracy and insight into airport capacity. This framework supports the development of more adaptive and resilient traffic management initiatives, ultimately improving operational efficiency and passenger experience across the national airspace system.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Model Features

The model aims to provide a comprehensive set of predictors for forecasting airport capacity over an 8-hour forecast window at 29 core U.S. airports. This forecast window was selected as it aligns with the planning horizon for strategic traffic flow management decisions such as GDPs, rerouting, and resource allocation. Building on past research [16], the scope of the models was expanded from a single airport to multiple key U.S. airports. This allows us to both generalize our model and analyze its predictive capabilities while addressing varying operational and meteorological conditions across different locations.

Data was collected from the Aviation System Performance Metrics (ASPM), the Terminal Aerodrome Forecast (TAF), and the High-Resolution Rapid Refresh (HRRR) datasets to generate the feature set used for model training. Weather predictions were issued hourly during the period of interest. To enable predictions with an eight-hour lookahead as needed for strategic ATM decision-making, the model utilized eight distinct sets of TAF and HRRR wind forecasts. Each set corresponded to a specific lookahead time but was issued prior to its utilization. For instance, at 9:00 a.m., a set of TAF and HRRR forecasts could be used to make the initial airport acceptance rate (AAR) and airport departure rate (ADR) predictions for 10:00 a.m., alongside other model features, provided both forecasts were issued before 9:00 a.m. Since TAF forecasts are not issued every hour, the most recent forecasts for the next eight hours were used. Any gaps in TAF data were filled using the forecasts from the previous hour.

The selected model features include:

Wind Speed and Direction: Runways are typically aligned to allow landings in headwind conditions, with strong tailwinds or crosswinds significantly disrupting operations. At airports with overflow runways, adverse wind conditions can result in runway closures, heavily impacting airport capacity. Wind speed and direction data were sourced from the TAF dataset.

Wind Gusts: Wind gusts are hazardous to aircraft in close proximity and may necessitate increased spacing between flights. This has an adverse effect on terminal airspace capacity. The inclusion of wind gusts accounts for these safety

driven spacing constraints. Wind gust data was sourced from the TAF dataset.

Ceiling and Visibility: Cloud ceiling levels and visibility impact air traffic controllers' (ATCOs) ability to maintain throughput. Airports operate most efficiently under Visual Meteorological Conditions (VMC), while Instrument Meteorological Conditions (IMC) require reliance on flight instruments increasing minimum separations between aircraft. TAF data on ceiling levels, cloud status, and visibility ranges was used. Visibility was taken directly, while cloud status was calculated as a weighted sum of cloud cover types: few (0.25), scattered (0.5), broken (0.75), and overcast (1.0). Sky ceiling was determined using the lowest feature among broken and overcast clouds or set to 30,000 feet if neither was present. Ceiling and visibility data was sourced from the TAF dataset.

HRRR Wind Data: In addition to conditions at the airport, winds along arrival routes were also considered. High winds can cause differing ground speeds between trailing and leading aircraft, leading to compression and increased spacing requirements to ensure safety. To account for this, wind speed and direction were extracted from seven HRRR surface-level locations for each airport: six distributed evenly along the circumference of a circle with a radius of 60 kilometers centered on the airport and one directly over the airport itself. To illustrate this process, we've shown the selected HRRR points for Newark airport in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. HRRR Sampling Locations around Newark Airport

Demand: The ASPM dataset provides flight schedule information for hourly arrivals and departures, serving as a proxy for airport demand. This addressed the lack of real-time operational data.

Current Capacity: Prior studies have found future AAR to be highly correlated with recent prior AAR [18, 19]. Accordingly, the model includes the current AAR at the time of forecast in its feature set. This was sourced from the ASPM dataset.

Time: Regular traffic volume fluctuations were captured by including the time of day, day of the week, and month as features, accounting for temporal variations in activity.

Output: The models are trained and tested against the Efficiency AAR as reported in the ASPM dataset. This represents the hourly arrival rate that an airport facility determines it can accommodate under prevailing conditions, including weather, runway configurations, and operational constraints such as staffing levels or equipment outages [20]. This rate is periodically updated throughout the day to reflect changes in these factors and serves as a benchmark for air traffic management performance. While actual arrivals may occasionally exceed the Efficiency AAR due to exceptional circumstances like increased staffing or optimal traffic sequencing, such instances are not indicative of sustainable operational capacity. Therefore, the Efficiency AAR provides a realistic and conservative estimate of an airport's arrival handling capability

This methodology ensures that all selected features capture critical operational and environmental factors while accommodating variations across the airports in the study. This provides robust and scalable predictive capabilities.

B. Model Architecture

After considering dense neural networks and gradient boosting approaches we opted to leverage recurrent neural networks (RNNs) for airport capacity prediction due to their capability to effectively model time-dependent datasets with a high degree of accuracy. These models showed significant performance benefits over alternative approaches in past research [16]. Specifically, Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) cells, a variant of RNNs, were utilized. LSTM cells are designed to capture long-term dependencies in sequential data by employing memory units and gating mechanisms, enabling them to selectively retain or update information over multiple time steps. This makes them particularly well-suited for time series prediction tasks.

The model architecture was constructed using TensorFlow's functional python API. We experimented with several model configurations before selecting the best performing architecture which consisted of a series of three dense layers with 256, 512, and 128 nodes respectively followed by an LSTM layer with 128 nodes and finally another dense layer with 32 nodes. Dense layers are composed of a set of neurons that receive input from all neurons in the

previous layer, perform a computation on that input, and then send the output to all neurons in the next layer. This allows dense layers to learn complex relationships between inputs and outputs by making connections between all neurons in the layer. LSTM layers are designed to handle sequential data and learn long-term dependencies between inputs. They work by maintaining a cell state that stores information over time, and using gates (input, output, and forget gates) to control the flow of information into and out of the cell state, allowing the network to selectively remember or forget information as needed. The full model architecture is illustrated in Fig. 2. These layers allowed the model to learn temporal dependencies and complex patterns in the input data. We found the model performed best when trained with a batch size of 32 and we implemented the ReduceLROnPlateau [20] module from TensorFlow, which reduces the learning rate each time the value loss plateaus to prevent overfitting while allowing the models to still explore a wide range of possible configurations. We used an initial learning rate of 0.01 and decreased it by a factor of 0.8 each time the model plateaued with a patience of 6 and a final cutoff for the learning rate of $1e-5$.

To enhance predictive capability, we utilized the pinball loss function illustrated in eq. 1 where P_α is the pinball loss, α is the desired quantile, y is the ground-truth AAR, and z is the forecasted quantile prediction.

$$P_\alpha(y, z) = (y - z)\alpha \quad \text{if } y \geq z \quad (1)$$

$$P_\alpha(y, z) = (z - y)(1 - \alpha) \quad \text{if } y < z$$

Pinball loss, also known as quantile loss, is a metric used to evaluate quantile regression models by measuring the deviation between predicted quantiles and actual values. It assigns asymmetric penalties depending on whether the prediction underestimates or overestimates the target, making it particularly useful for modeling uncertainties. The loss function is defined such that if the actual value is greater than or equal to the predicted quantile, the error is scaled by the quantile level α , otherwise, the error is scaled by $(1 - \alpha)$. This property allows pinball loss to focus on specific quantiles rather than the mean, making it more robust for capturing distributional characteristics in heteroskedastic data. Unlike traditional metrics like mean squared error, pinball loss is

Figure 2. Model Architecture

well-suited for applications such as probabilistic forecasting, financial risk estimation, and demand prediction, where understanding different quantile levels is critical [21]. We trained the models to predict distinct quantiles ranging from the 5th to 95th in steps of 5. This approach allowed for a more robust modeling of uncertainty in our predictions.

To simulate the real-world use case for airport capacity predictions, the models were all trained on data from 2018 before being tested and trained online in parallel with data from 2019. During online training, 2019 data was processed one day at a time. For each day, the model's performance was tested, and the past 24 hours of data (lagged by eight hours to prevent overlap and avoid information leakage) were used to update the model. This sequential training process ensured that the model learned from recent data while maintaining the integrity of its predictions.

By incorporating these design elements, the LSTM-based model demonstrated the ability to effectively predict airport capacity and runway configurations while accounting for temporal dependencies and uncertainty in the data.

C. Random Correlated Capacity Draws

The final step in our methodology was to use the generated quantile predictions to create a set of random correlated draws of the airport capacities. This results in a set of feasible capacity scenarios which should accurately reflect the uncertainty in our capacity predictions and forecasts. These weather scenarios can then be passed into other tools for TMI planning to determine optimal TMIs given the expected airport demand and other applicable factors.

We used an autoregressive approach to generate a set of 30 random correlated capacity draws at each airport for all forecasts according to eq. 2 where y_t is the selected quantile for hour t , y_0 is a randomly selected quantile for the first hour, β_1 is the coefficient of correlation which defines the importance of the previously selected quantile, we used 0.8 to impart a strong correlation between past and future draws. ϵ_t is the random error term for which we used a normal distribution about 0 with a standard deviation of 0.1 to allow for minor quantile changes while having a low chance for large jumps. This results in a tendency for the draw to remain near the initially selected quantile but still introduces random developments. We set β_0 dependent upon β_1 and y_0 to avoid a collapse to the lowest or highest quantiles.

$$\begin{aligned} y_t &= (\beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot y_{t-1} + \epsilon_t) \\ \beta_0 &= (1 - \beta_1) \cdot y_0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

An example random correlated draw for Newark Liberty International Airport (EWR) is shown below in Fig. 3. The draw initially starts at the 25th quantile and quickly moves up to the 35th quantile at the second hour. It then drops to the 20th quantile in the 5th hour before settling on the 30th quantile at the end of the forecast.

Figure 3. Example Correlated Random Capacity Draw

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Experimental Description

We will first examine a test case of the proposed model at EWR to illustrate how the model's predictions behave at various quantiles. We then analyze the model's performance for predicting airport capacity across 29 core U.S. airports. Predictions were generated for look ahead times extending up to 8 hours, allowing for a detailed examination of performance across temporal horizons.

The primary evaluation metric for quantile models is the pinball loss function, which quantifies prediction error across the quantile distribution. We examine two forms of pinball loss: the absolute pinball loss and the fractional pinball loss normalized by the median airport capacity of the given airport. This dual analysis provides insights into both the absolute and relative error magnitudes.

We also examine the mean absolute error (MAE) and root mean square error (RMSE) of the expected AAR value across quantiles. This is computed by taking the mean of our model's predictions for each quantile, and comparing that to the actual value using the RMSE formula shown in eq. 3 where n is the number of samples, y_i is the observed value, and \hat{y}_i is the predicted value. Additionally, we examine the fractional RMSE normalized by the median airport capacity for each airport.

$$RMSE = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 / n \right)^{0.5} \quad (3)$$

To assess the model's ability to generate realistic capacity scenarios, we use an autoregressive approach to produce 30 random correlated draws across the quantile distribution. These draws capture the variability and uncertainty inherent in airport capacity predictions while preserving temporal dependencies to produce a set of feasible weather scenarios.

This setup enables us to evaluate the model's accuracy and robustness comprehensively, with a focus on practical utility for operational decision-making in airport management.

B. Newark Liberty International Airport Test Case

Before going through the results for all airports, we will first examine a specific test case at Newark Liberty International Airport (EWR) where we observed several drops and peaks in capacity for March 1st to 6th, 2019. The predicted versus actual AARs for EWR at the 25th, 50th, and 75th quantiles for the above time range are shown in Fig. 4-6. At the 25th quantile the model is incentivized to focus on capturing the drops in capacity over accurately predicting the peaks. We can see the model performs well at predicting the various drops in capacity from hours 10 to 25 as well as the drop in capacity at hour 85. The model does not perform as well during the drop at hour 95. In this case, the time of the predicted drop in capacity is lagged by the lead time which implies the model was not able to recognize the drop until it had already occurred. At the 25th quantile the model often fails to recognize the peaks in capacity when they occur. The peaks at hours 132 and 156 are almost entirely missed at this quantile. Additionally, we can see the model hallucinated a drop in capacity around hour 50 which never occurred. These instances are more common at the extreme ends of the quantile spectrum. The 25th quantile model prioritizes staying under the ground-truth AAR while still attempting to capture the rise and fall in capacity throughout the examined time frame.

At the 50th quantile the model is equally penalized for predicting above or below the ground truth AAR, as such this is the level we would expect to match the ground truth AAR most frequently. Compared to the 25th quantile, this model does a much better job at capturing the peaks in capacity, however it is still delayed in its predictions. The model performed similarly to the 25th quantile on the drops at hours 10 and 95, however it missed the drop at hour 85 and overestimated the capacity from hour 47 to 66. Unlike the 25th quantile, the 50th quantile model did not hallucinate a drop in capacity at hour 50, staying much closer to the ground-truth AAR.

The 75th quantile model did a much better job of predicting the peaks than the 25th or 50th quantiles. The two observed peaks were accurately predicted at each hour of lead time. The model was not able to accurately predict the drops at this quantile, only somewhat recognizing the drops in capacity around hour 20 and 60 while completely missing the others. At this quantile the model is incentivized to stay above the ground truth AAR so it is unsurprising that the model was not able to predict the drops in capacity.

Figure 4. 25th Quantile Predictions of AAR at EWR from Mar 1st to 6th 2019

Figure 5. 50th Quantile Predictions of AAR at EWR from Mar 1st to 6th 2019

Figure 6. 75th Quantile Predictions of AAR at EWR from Mar 1st to 6th 2019

Each of the examined quantiles was quite successful when predicting at the standard AAR of 40 for EWR. This behavior was also observed when predicting the AAR at EWR in a past paper [22] and is generally consistent for all the examined airports in this paper.

C. Core 29 US Airports

To illustrate the performance of the quantile models at a broad set of airports, we employ the pinball loss metric defined in eq. 1. We examine the mean pinball loss on all of our 2019 data across all quantiles for each hour of lead time. This provides insight into how the predictive performance of the models vary as they predict farther into the future. These results can be viewed in Table I and Fig. 7.

We can see there is a large range in performance between the examined airports. The majority of airports start out with a pinball loss of less than one with one hour of lead time, and the loss steadily increases till the majority of airports have a pinball loss of under two at eight hours of lead time. However, for some airports we see significantly worse performance. Most notably Charlotte Douglas International Airport (CLT) shows a steep increase in pinball loss as the lead time increases until it is over 5.5 at eight hours of lead time. There are several factors which could cause these differences in performance. Airports which experience more traffic or employ a greater number of runway configurations are more likely to show a

higher pinball loss as the model has a greater range of potential AARs to choose from. Region specific climate factors or traffic management strategies could also impact the AAR in ways our model parameters don't account for. Adding additional model parameters which measure the complexity of runway configurations may help improve model performance.

TABLE I. ABSOLUTE PINBALL LOSS BY AIRPORT AND LEAD TIME

Airport Code	Absolute Pinball Loss of AAR predictions by Lead Time							
	1hr	2hrs	3hrs	4hrs	5hrs	6hrs	7hrs	8hrs
ATL	0.48	0.63	0.77	0.89	0.98	1.08	1.17	1.26
BOS	0.88	1.14	1.41	1.67	1.94	2.18	2.39	2.57
BWI	0.14	0.18	0.21	0.24	0.27	0.29	0.30	0.32
CLT	1.45	2.14	2.79	3.45	4.07	4.71	5.27	5.58
DCA	0.17	0.19	0.21	0.24	0.26	0.28	0.30	0.32
DEN	2.91	2.94	2.96	3.00	3.06	3.13	3.22	3.30
DFW	1.04	1.18	1.35	1.45	1.54	1.61	1.68	1.73
DTW	2.00	2.42	2.76	2.98	3.24	3.47	3.73	3.95
EWR	0.39	0.45	0.54	0.63	0.70	0.76	0.81	0.84
FLL	2.16	2.36	2.53	2.52	2.53	2.56	2.59	2.62
IAD	0.60	0.74	0.87	1.00	1.11	1.22	1.32	1.42
IAH	1.31	1.38	1.53	1.66	1.77	1.87	1.96	2.05
JFK	0.76	0.97	1.13	1.29	1.43	1.53	1.62	1.69
LAS	0.49	0.55	0.64	0.71	0.76	0.80	0.84	0.88
LAX	0.66	0.53	0.55	0.57	0.60	0.63	0.66	0.68
LGA	0.73	1.05	1.35	1.59	1.79	1.92	1.98	2.02
MCO	0.61	0.68	0.74	0.80	0.85	0.90	0.94	0.98
MDW	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.12	0.12	0.13	0.13	0.13
MEM	0.84	1.17	1.50	1.79	2.02	2.21	2.34	2.41
MIA	0.66	0.68	0.69	0.70	0.71	0.72	0.73	0.74
MSP	0.66	0.84	0.95	1.03	1.08	1.12	1.17	1.21
ORD	0.91	0.98	1.08	1.19	1.28	1.35	1.42	1.49
PHL	0.58	0.73	0.85	0.96	1.04	1.12	1.20	1.28
PHX	0.63	0.77	0.88	0.98	1.06	1.13	1.19	1.24
SAN	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
SEA	0.23	0.28	0.32	0.35	0.38	0.41	0.44	0.46
SFO	0.92	1.33	1.68	2.03	2.38	2.70	3.03	3.33
SLC	0.37	0.46	0.58	0.69	0.80	0.90	1.00	1.08
TPA	1.07	0.68	0.65	0.66	0.66	0.66	0.66	0.66

Most of the core US airports have a standard AAR which the airport operates at the majority of the time. This value is different for each airport and depends upon the runway configuration, environmental factors, and ATCOs. In order to account for the difference in standard capacity between airports we normalized the pinball losses by the median AAR for each airport, the results are shown in Fig. 8.

The fractional pinball loss for most airports ranges from under 0.01 with one hour of lead time to 0.02 with eight hours of lead time, or 1-2% of the standard capacity. However, we see that SFO, BOS, CLT, and LGA all reach a fractional pinball loss of over 0.05 at eight hours of lead time while FLL shows fairly consistent if unideal performance ranging from about 0.04 to 0.05 over all hours of lead time. The large range in performance suggests that there are additional factors affecting the AAR at these poorly performing airports which our models are not adequately capturing.

While pinball loss is an effective metric for comparing various quantile models, it is not obvious how pinball loss relates to the true accuracy of the model. To rectify this, we examined the RMSE and MAE of the expected AAR from each of our quantile models. It should be noted that these models were optimized for quantile predictions so lower performance is to be expected when evaluating them based on RMSE or MAE. The RMSEs of the AAR predictions can be seen in Fig. 9 and the MAEs in Fig. 10.

Figure 8. Fractional Pinball Loss of AAR Predictions for Core 29 US Airports by Lead Time

Figure 7. Pinball Loss of AAR Predictions for Core 29 US Airports by Lead Time

Figure 9. RMSE of Expected Value AAR Predictions for Core 29 US Airports by Lead Time

Figure 10. MAE of Expected Value AAR Predictions for Core 29 US Airports by Lead Time

We observe a large range in RMSEs and MAEs across the various airports examined. At some airports including SAN, DCA, BWI, MDW, and SEA we show very low RMSEs of under two aircraft per hour for most lead times. The majority of airport models achieved an RMSE of between two and five aircraft per hour at one hour of lead time which gradually increased to between three and ten aircraft per hour at eight hours of lead time. However, several airport models performed far worse with CLT standing out for reaching an RMSE of over 20 aircraft per hour at eight hours of lead time. DEN and DTW also reached quite high RMSEs of 13 and 14 respectively at eight hours of lead time. This could be partly due to some airports experiencing much greater levels of traffic with DEN, CLT, and DTW having relatively high standard rates of 114, 87 and 80 while SAN, DCA, BWI, MDW and SEA have significantly lower standard rates of 24, 34, 36, 36, and 46 respectively. As with the pinball loss metric, we will also examine the RMSEs normalized by the standard arrival rate to better understand these errors in the contexts of the airports in question. This data is plotted in Fig. 11.

Figure 11. Fractional RMSE of Expected Value AAR Predictions for Core 29 US Airports by Lead Time

The fractional RMSEs continue to show a very large range in the models' predictive performance at various airports. The fractional RMSE is under 0.02 for SAN at all lead times however for LGA the fractional RMSE starts out at 0.12 and plateaus at over 0.25 from the fifth hour on. This large range in fractional RMSEs suggests that there are various factors affecting how easy it is to predict the AAR at the different airports. It is likely that our models are missing some key parameters which play a large role in determining the capacity at airports like LGA, BOS, SFO, and CLT. This could potentially be addressed by incorporating convective weather parameters into the model or dynamically adjusting the HRRR sampling locations for each airport according to their runway configurations.

D. Convective Weather

To determine what effect convective weather might be having on the models' predictive performances, we looked at a subset of the airports examined and split up forecasts which included convective weather from those that did not. From our 2019 test cases, we identified 1383, 760, 791, 774, and 667 forecasts that included convective weather for BOS, EWR, JFK, LGA, and PHL respectively. The RMSEs for these two subsets of with/without convective weather are shown in Fig. 12 and Fig.13.

In the non-convective weather cases, we see a significant decrease in the RMSE for EWR, JFK, and PHL. Each of these airports shows a decrease in the RMSE of around two aircraft per hour at each lead time. At BOS, we see that in the cases without convective weather, the lead time has a greater impact on the RMSE with better performance at one hour of lead time but worse performance at eight hours. Interestingly, LGA shows significantly better performance in convective weather cases at all lead times with the RMSE plateauing around 6.5 aircraft per hour compared to 10 aircraft per hour in the non-convective case. While it is clear that convective weather has a significant impact on our models' predictive performance, the impact is not consistent so it is hard to draw more conclusions without incorporating forecasts of convective weather into our model parameters.

Figure 12. RMSE of Expected Value AAR Predictions for 5 Airports in Convective Weather

Figure 13. RMSE of Expected Value AAR Predictions for 5 Airports in Non-Convective Weather

E. Correlated Random Draws

For each airport we generated a set of 30 random correlated draws on each of the forecasts. These represent the range of expected capacity scenarios and can be used by TMI planning tools to optimize airport operations to a specified level of acceptable risk. An example set of correlated draws on EWR from March 3, 2019 is shown in Fig. 14. We can see that most of the generated scenarios are within a couple of aircraft per hour of the ground truth AAR (shown in black) for the entire forecast. However, as we reach a lead time of 6 hours, several of the scenarios experience a steep drop in capacity which is not reflected in the ground truth AAR. This is likely due to a combination of the lower quantiles being overly cautious when sensing a drop and the model as a whole being less confident when predicting at less common rates like 38. Notably the ground-truth AAR remains within the bounds of the scenarios for the entire forecast duration. This was also seen in the vast majority of test cases suggesting that the quantile models are adequately encapsulating the possible ranges of the AARs.

Figure 14. Random Correlated Capacity Draws on EWR

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

A. Conclusions

In this paper we have presented a comprehensive evaluation of our model's performance in predicting airport capacity at various quantiles.

The results of the test case at EWR demonstrated the model's ability to accurately predict drops and peaks in capacity. Quantile specific analyses revealed that the models effectively captured capacity trends but exhibited distinct behavior based on their optimization objectives. The 25th quantile model excelled in predicting capacity drops but underperformed in capturing peaks, whereas the 75th quantile model demonstrated the opposite trend. The 50th quantile model provided a balanced performance, aligning closely with ground-truth values. These results emphasize the potential benefits of tailoring quantile specific predictions to operational objectives. For example, if demand is high and the system is at risk of congestion, air traffic managers might use a high quantile capacity forecast to allow more arrivals and departures, reducing delays if conditions allow. Similarly, if storms, fog, or other adverse conditions are expected or if controller availability is low, ATCOs may be more risk adverse opting for a lower quantile capacity forecast to prevent causing major disruptions and ensure manageable workload levels.

The evaluation of the model's performance across 29 core US airports revealed a large range in performance between airports, with some airports performing significantly better than others. The pinball loss, MAE, and RMSE metrics demonstrated that most airports achieved acceptable prediction accuracy, with steady increases in error as lead time extended. However, certain airports, such as CLT, LGA, BOS and SFO showed significantly higher errors across all metrics, indicating challenges in predicting the capacity at these locations. The use of the pinball loss function, MAE, and RMSE as evaluation metrics provided a comprehensive understanding of the model's performance.

The incorporation of convective weather conditions provided additional context for understanding the model's performance in adverse weather. Airports such as EWR, JFK, and PHL showed significantly reduced errors in non-convective weather cases, underscoring the need for more robust convective weather forecast parameters in the models. However, inconsistencies in the relationship between weather and prediction accuracy at other airports, such as LGA, and BOS suggest that more research is needed to fully determine the impact of convective weather on airport capacity predictions.

The random correlated draws provided a range of likely capacity scenarios for TMI planning, closely aligning with ground truth AAR. While deviations appear at longer lead times, the ground-truth AAR remained within scenario bounds, indicating the models effectively captured AAR variability.

This study has demonstrated models which effectively captured trends at different quantiles but faced trade-offs between accurately predicting capacity peaks and drops. The wide range of performance across airports highlights the importance of location-specific factors, such as runway configurations and operational constraints. Convective weather remains a critical factor influencing prediction

accuracy, suggesting potential improvements by incorporating dynamic weather features into the models. Autoregressive scenario generation was also demonstrated which produced realistic capacity scenarios. These scenarios could provide valuable insights for operational decision-making. The results of this study have implications for the development of more accurate and reliable airport capacity prediction models, which are essential for informing operational decision-making in airport management.

B. Future Work

Improving prediction accuracy at problematic airports, will likely require incorporating additional parameters, particularly those related to local environmental and operational conditions. Expanding the model to include convective weather forecasts or additional forecast models such as the Localized Aviation MOS Program (LAMP) [23] and dynamically adjusting parameters based on airport-specific characteristics may further enhance performance. Additionally, it would be useful to compare our performance to alternative model architectures such as MF-Transformers on the same set of input data. These refinements will help bridge the gap between model predictions and real-world variability, ensuring greater reliability and utility for airport management and planning.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank Pat Lamey, Mike Matthews, Dave Johnson, Margo Pawlak, and Kim Woodrow for their help in acquiring the High-Resolution Rapid Refresh weather forecast data used in this analysis.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bureau of Transportation Statistics, "Causes of National Aviation System Delays National (January - December, 2023)," 2024, https://www.transtats.bts.gov/ot_delay/ot_delaycause1.asp?6B2r=I&20=E
- [2] L. Delgado, X. Prats, and B. Sridhar, "Cruise speed reduction for ground delay programs: A case study for San Francisco International Airport arrivals," *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 36, 2013, pp. 83-96.
- [3] J.C. Jones and D.J. Lovell, "Methods for curbing the exemption bias in ground delay programs through speed control," in *Transportation Research Record: Journal of the Transportation Research Board*, 2400 (1), 2014, pp. 37-44.
- [4] J. C. Jones, D. J. Lovell, and M. O. Ball, "Combining Control by CTA and Dynamic Enroute Speed Adjustment to Improve Ground Delay Program Performance," In *11th USA/Europe ATM R&D Seminar (ATM 2015)*, Lisbon, 2015.
- [5] H. Swenson, J.E. Robinson III and J. Steve Winter, "NASA's ATM Technology Demonstration-1: Moving NextGen Arrival Concepts from the Laboratory to the Operational NAS," In *Journal of Air Traffic Control*, 55(2), 2013, 27-37.
- [6] T. Prevot, B. Baxley, T. Callantine, W. Johnson, L. Quon, J. Robinson, H. N. Swenson, "NASA's ATM Technology Demonstration-1: Transitioning fuel efficient, high throughput arrival operations from simulation to reality," *Proceedings of the International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction in Aerospace (HCI-Aero 2012)*, Brussels, 2012.
- [7] T. G. Reynolds, M. McPartland, T. Teller, and S. Troxel, "Exploring Wind Information Requirements for Four Dimensional Trajectory-Based Operations," *11th USA/Europe Air Traffic Management Research and Development Seminar*, 2015.
- [8] C. Edwards, Y. Glina, J. Jones, M. McPartland, T. Reynolds, S. Troxel, "Methods of Selecting Forecast Winds for Flight Management Systems to Support Four-Dimensional Trajectory-Based Operations," *16th AIAA Aviation Technology, Integration, and Operations Conference*, 2016, (p. 4069).
- [9] M.O. Ball, R. Hoffman, A.R. Odoni, and R. Rifkin, "A stochastic integer program with dual network structure and its application to the ground-holding problem," *Operations Research*, 51(1), 2003, pp.167-171.
- [10] A. Mukherjee, and M. Hansen, "A dynamic stochastic model for the single airport ground holding problem," *Transportation Science*, 41(4), 2007, pp.444-456.
- [11] R. A. DeLaura, R. F. Ferris, F. M. Robasky, S. W. Troxel and N. K. Underhill, "Initial Assessment of Wind Forecasts for Airport Acceptance Rate (AAR) and Ground Delay Program (GDP) Planning," *Project Report ATC-414*, MIT Lincoln Laboratory, Lexington, MA, 2014.
- [12] James C. Jones, Richard DeLaura, Margo Pawlak, Seth Troxel, Ngaire Underhill, "Predicting & Quantifying Risk in Airport Capacity Profile Selection for Air Traffic Management," *Twelfth USA/Europe Air Traffic Management Research and Development Seminar*, 2017.
- [13] Du, Wenbo, Shenwen Chen, Haitao Li, Zhishuai Li, Xianbin Cao, and Yisheng Lv, "Airport Capacity Prediction With Multisource Features: A Temporal Deep Learning Approach," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* 24, 2022, no. 1: 615-630.
- [14] Kicing, Rafal, Jit-Tat Chen, Matthias Steiner, and James Pinto, "Airport capacity prediction with explicit consideration of weather forecast uncertainty," *Journal of Air Transportation* 24, 2016, no. 1: 18-28.
- [15] B. Tolley and J. Jones, "Predicting Airport Capacities Using Neural Networks," *2024 Integrated Communications, Navigation and Surveillance Conference (ICNS)*, Herndon, VA, USA, 2024, pp. 1-10, doi: 10.1109/ICNS60906.2024.10550818.
- [16] Shin-Lai (Alex) Tien, Christine Taylor, Erik Vargo, and Craig Wanke, "Using Ensemble Weather Forecasts for Predicting Airport Arrival Capacity," *Journal of Air Transportation*, 2018, 26:3 pp. 123-132
- [17] T. G. Puranik, M. Memarzadeh, and K. M. Kalyanam, "Predicting Airport Runway Configurations for Decision-Support Using Supervised Learning," in *2023 IEEE/AIAA 42nd Digital Avionics Systems Conference (DASC)*, San Antonio, TX, USA, 2023, pp. 1-10, doi: 10.1109/DASC58513.2023.10311186.
- [18] C. Provan, L. Cook, and J. Cunningham, "A probabilistic airport capacity model for improved ground delay program planning," *Digital Aviation Systems Conference*, 2011.
- [19] J. Cunningham, L. Cook, and C. Provan, "The Utilization of Current Forecast Products in a Probabilistic Airport Capacity Model," *AMS Annual Meeting*, American Meteorological Soc., Boston, 2012, Paper 540.
- [20] Federal Aviation Administration (FAA). *ASPM AERO: Definitions of Variables*. https://aspm.faa.gov/aspmhelp/index/ASPM_AERO_Definitions_of_Variables.html. [Accessed May 20, 2025].
- [21] TensorFlow, "tf.keras.callbacks.ReduceLROnPlateau," *TensorFlow API Documentation*, Jun. 7, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.tensorflow.org/api_docs/python/tf/keras/callbacks/ReduceLROnPlateau. [Accessed: Jan. 28, 2025].
- [22] Ingo Steinwart, Andreas Christmann. "Estimating conditional quantiles with the help of the pinball loss." *Bernoulli* 17 (1) 211 - 225, February 2011. <https://doi.org/10.3150/10-BEJ267>
- [23] Rudack, David E. "An Introduction to the Localized Aviation MOS Program (LAMP)". *National Weather Service, Meteorological Development Laboratory*. 2008. <https://www.weather.gov/media/mdl/Rudack2008.pdf>.

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Benjamin Tolley is Associate Staff in the Air Traffic Control & Weather Systems Group at MIT Lincoln Laboratory. He has a M.S. in Physics from Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute.

Jeremiah Budiman is Associate Staff in the Air Traffic Control & Weather Systems Group at MIT Lincoln

Laboratory. He has an M.Eng. in Electrical Engineering and Computer Science from Massachusetts Institute of Technology.

James C. Jones is Technical Staff in the Air Traffic Control & Weather Systems Group at MIT Lincoln Laboratory. He has a PhD in Civil and Environmental Engineering from the University of Maryland.